

1 **Pondscape or waterscape? The effect on the diversity of dispersal along**
2 **different freshwater ecosystems**

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13 **Abstract**

14 Dispersal is a main determinant of community assembly. Landscape configurations of

15 rivers, lakes or ponds are often independently considered in this framework. However,

16 these systems share species conforming to a waterscape with different environments

17 coupled by dispersal. While empirical results support a main role of this coupling on

18 biodiversity organization, it is difficult to assess its importance at large geographic scales.

19 Using a theoretical approach, we quantified the potential role of dispersal through

20 different freshwater ecosystems of the United Kingdom and Ireland on biogeographic

21 diversity patterns. We implemented a coalescent model considering 11,131 communities

22 connected by distance-dependent dispersal and with species that have different

23 performances for recruitment in three different aquatic habitats. Biogeographic diversity

24 patterns were estimated for each habitat alone or for the whole waterscape combining
25 ephemeral, temporal, and permanent waters. The results indicated that the coupling
26 between different types of environments fostered local diversity, in a magnitude that
27 increased from the ephemeral to permanent waters and from poorer to richer
28 communities. Furthermore, a strong spatial structure in the potential effect of dispersal
29 among different freshwater environments was observed, indicating that freshwater
30 biogeography was likely determined by the connection among freshwater ecosystems to
31 a larger extent than previously thought.

32

33 **Keywords (4-6):** *Metacommunity; Freshwater habitats; Biogeography; Mass effect;*
34 *Connectivity*

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36

37 **INTRODUCTION**

38 Dispersal through the landscape connecting the dynamics of different local communities
39 is now recognized as a significant determinant of biodiversity organization (Matias et al.,
40 2013; Borthagaray et al., 2015a; Leibold & Chase, 2018). This recognition is forcing the
41 explicit consideration of the landscape configuration of ecosystems and its effect on
42 species dispersal to improve the understanding of community assembly and resilience
43 (Leibold & Chase, 2018; Borthagaray et al., 2020; Cunillera-Montcusí et al., 2021).
44 Consequently, a metacommunity network capturing the dispersal among local
45 communities may be considered (Economio & Keitt, 2008, 2010). These networks have
46 been used to represent the landscape configuration of rivers (Altermatt, 2013; Seymour
47 et al., 2015; Borthagaray et al., 2020), ponds (Borthagaray et al., 2015b; Cunillera-

48 Montcusí et al., 2021), vegetation patches (Borthagaray et al., 2012), and oceanic islands
49 (Bender et al., 2017), among others. When representing landscape configuration and
50 dispersal, only a single type of ecosystem is generally considered. However, different
51 kinds of ecosystems usually share species representing a mutual source of individuals
52 (Williams et al., 2004; Biggs et al., 2017; Borthagaray et al., 2018). Congruently, studies
53 performed at local scales have indicated that the flow of individuals among different
54 environments may represent important determinants of local community richness
55 (Williams et al., 2004, 2020; Hill et al., 2017a).

56 Freshwater environments comprise a wide range of ecosystems from ponds and
57 streams to lakes and rivers. Some species are observed only in one kind of freshwater.
58 For example, some amphibian species are adapted or prefer temporal fishless habitats
59 (Miró et al., 2020), a habitat is also favorable to other specific taxa (Deil, 2005; Williams,
60 2006; Chase & Shulman, 2009; Boix et al., 2016). Other species are adapted to running
61 waters or deep stratified lakes (Rosset et al., 2017; Bastin et al., 2019). These different
62 compositions of specialists ultimately create a mosaic of specialized species within a
63 region comprised of these different habitats. However, there are also many species that
64 are observed in different kinds of freshwater ecosystems (Biggs et al., 2017) or even
65 specialists that sporadically use other habitats (e.g., amphibians; Buono et al., 2019). In
66 southern England, Biggs et al. (2017) and Williams et al. (2004) reported that in ponds,
67 rivers, streams, and ditches, of the 230 aquatic macroinvertebrate taxa recorded, 33%
68 were found only in ponds, 32% were found only in rivers and 45% were found in both
69 ponds and rivers. This highlights the great shared part of diversity that different habitats
70 (lotic or lentic) can present and the limitations that we can face when focusing only on a
71 specific habitat—as ponds—and its regional context—the pondscape (Hill et al., 2021).

72 Even if the performance of species differs among environments, communities
73 from these environments may be mutually affected by two landscape processes. First,
74 they could be affected by a stepping-stone dynamic in which the dispersal among
75 favorable patches is enhanced by the use of patches for which the species could be less
76 adapted (Heino et al., 2021). Second, there may be a mass effect in which local richness
77 is enhanced by species that persist because of the flux of individuals from more favorable
78 environments (Brown & Kodric-Brown, 1977; Loreau, 2010). However, it should be
79 noted that the mass effect can also reduce local diversity when the regional dominance of
80 a species is translated to local dominance, thus determining the local and regional
81 extinction of other species (Loreau 2010; Leibold and chase 2018). Despite the evidence
82 for the role of dispersal between different freshwater environments in the assembly of
83 communities (Williams et al., 2004; Biggs et al., 2017; Hill et al., 2021), increasing our
84 understanding of its potential consequences at larger geographic patterns of biodiversity
85 is a pressing challenge. Understanding this connection is particularly important in the
86 context of landscape degradation affecting the dispersal processes of several species
87 (Haddad et al., 2015; Thompson et al., 2017). However, at the geographic spatial scale,
88 experimental approaches are logistically impossible (Shipley et al., 2016), and empirical
89 approaches are limited by sampling capacities and because biotic degradation after
90 landscape reconfiguration may take decades or centuries to become evident (Halley &
91 Iwasa, 2011). Theoretical approaches may be particularly valuable in this framework,
92 complementing empirical results about the landscape dispersal-diversity connection and
93 inferring its consequences at biogeographic scales (Worm and Tittensor, 2018; Cunillera-
94 Montcusí et al., 2021).

95 In this work, we attempted to advance the understanding of the potential role of
96 dispersal between different freshwater environments in the biogeographic patterns of

97 diversity using the United Kingdom and Ireland as a case study. To this aim, using the
98 Global Surface Water database (see Pekel et al., 2016), we represented the waterscapes
99 by a grid of 10×10 km cells, classifying surface waters in each cell as ephemeral,
100 temporal, and permanent on the basis of their frequency of occurrence. Then, a coalescent
101 metacommunity model was run estimating the effect of landscape configuration on the
102 diversity pattern when different freshwater environments were mutually isolated versus
103 when dispersal among freshwater ecosystems was permitted. Notably, waterscape
104 configuration and dispersal among different freshwater ecosystems were indicated as key
105 processes determining biogeographic diversity patterns in all freshwater environments of
106 the United Kingdom and Ireland.

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108

109 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

110 *The waterscape*

111 The waterscape of the United Kingdom and Ireland was built from available satellite
112 imagery from the Global Surface Water database (Pekel et al., 2016). This database
113 provides wider-scale regional information for any type of waterbody and also has
114 information that could be translated to differentiate different types of freshwater habitats
115 (i.e., seasonality). Pekel et al. (2016) gathered images between the 16th of March 1984
116 and the 10th of October 2015 from the Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM), the Landsat 7
117 Enhanced Thematic Mapper-plus (ETM+) and the Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager
118 (OLI) orthorectified, top-of-atmosphere reflectance and brightness temperature images
119 (L1T). Pekel et al. (2016) classified each pixel as open water, as land or as a nonvalid
120 observation (see details in Pekel et al., 2016). In this sense, open water was defined as
121 any stretch of water larger than 30×30 m and open to the sky. This database constitutes

122 one of the best currently available databases considering freshwater habitats at a
123 biogeographic scale that also includes seasonality information. Due to satellite and image
124 processing limitations (see Pekel et al., 2016), it was not possible to identify small water
125 habitats—i.e., those smaller than 30×30 m were not considered in this study. However,
126 available information may represent a proxy of different water covers not explicitly
127 detected. As the database is based on several images recorded across years, the
128 seasonality of each pixel was also available, ranging from 1, an ephemeral pixel that had
129 barely any water during the analyzed period, to 100, a permanent pixel with water
130 detected throughout the whole period. Based on these, we selected and used the
131 “Occurrence dataset” containing surface water and seasonality.

132 Then, we used ArcGIS Pro to carry out all the data cartographic management,
133 mostly using ArcToolbox>Spatial Analyst Tools (ESRI Inc., 2020), and we extracted and
134 used only United Kingdom and Ireland pixel information. We defined a grid with cells of
135 10×10 km, grouping all the pixels within a cell according to three main categories of
136 water habitats: permanent (water surfaces with seasonality from 90 to 100), temporary
137 (water surfaces with seasonality ranging from 10 to 89) and ephemeral (water surfaces
138 with seasonality from 1 to 9). Using relative subjective thresholds, this categorization
139 provides a proxy of landscape configuration for three main freshwater habitats for which
140 specialist and generalist species can be identified (Davis & Bidwell, 2008; Biggs et al.,
141 2017; Kelly-Quinn et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2020). Based on the results of this
142 procedure, the waterscape of all the United Kingdom and Ireland is represented by 11,131
143 local communities of ephemeral, temporal, and permanent waters. In each cell, the
144 centroid and the percentage of water area occupied by each of the three types of habitats
145 were estimated. We considered this waterscape as a snapshot of all the potential habitat

146 surfaces that our study area could have; therefore, we considered its maximum capacity
147 relative to the years captured by Pekel et al. (2016).

148

149 *Metacommunity model*

150 We used a coalescent metacommunity model to infer the effect of organism dispersal
151 through different habitats on the local richness of ephemeral, temporal, and permanent
152 freshwater (Munoz et al., 2018; Worm & Tittensor, 2018; Cunillera-Montcusí et al.,
153 2021). Coalescent models are based exclusively on the filling dynamics of communities
154 representing an alternative to lottery models in which diversity emerges after a large
155 number of colonization-extinction iterations (Hubbell 2001). As a consequence,
156 coalescent models can deal with the simulation of assembly processes in large
157 metacommunities, producing similar predictions of geographic diversity patterns (Munoz
158 et al., 2018; Worm & Tittensor, 2018; Cunillera-Montcusí et al., 2021). Our coalescent
159 model started by selecting one individual from the species pool for each of the defined
160 local communities. Each local community has a size (J_i), which is proportional to the
161 amount of surface water contained on the grid cell. Thus, J_i defines the number of
162 individuals in each specific cell, which is determined by the area of the cell occupied by
163 water, A_j —i.e., $J_i = (J_{max}/A_{max}^{0.5}) * A_j^{0.5}$ being $J_{max} = 400$ and $A_{max} = 100$. Then,
164 communities are filled with J individuals who are sampled 1) from the metacommunity
165 species pool, 2) from neighboring communities, or 3) from the same local community
166 with probabilities $m.pool$ ($= 0.01$) (Worm & Tittensor, 2018), $m.neighbor$, and $1 -$
167 $(m.pool + m.neighbor)$. The dispersal kernel between two ponds determining the
168 $m.neighbor$ was modeled with an exponential decay function as $m.neighbor = m.max *$
169 $e^{-b*d_{ij}}$ where d_{ij} is the Euclidean distance between communities i and j , $m.max$ is the
170 migration between ponds 0 km apart ($m.max = 1$), b is a migration parameter defined by

171 the distance between ponds at which migration decays to half its maximum value, and
172 d_{50} is thus 4 km (distance between centroids of neighboring cells). Following previous
173 approaches (e.g., Gilarranz and Bascompte 2012, Cunillera-Montcusi et al 2021) a single
174 dispersal distance is considered here as reference value. It should be noted that larger
175 dispersal distance will magnify the dispersal effect between environments, and the
176 opposite is true. Moreover, this value of d_{50} was selected to represent a neighbor dispersal
177 process that could also propagate to distant communities (Tittensor & Worm 2016; Worm
178 & Tittensor 2018). Neighbor dispersal has been successfully used for modeling the effect
179 of large-scale metacommunity processes on biogeographic diversity patterns (Tittensor
180 & Worm 2016; Worm & Tittensor 2018). Using these dispersal processes, a community-
181 by-community migration matrix M was then estimated, with elements m_{ij} representing
182 the dispersal rate from community i to community j . Self-recruitment was fixed as one
183 setting the diagonal of the migration matrix M to one. The potential incoming migration
184 rate for a local community was represented by the columns of the migration matrix M
185 plus the migration from the pool. These values were standardized to add 1, as
186 $m_{ij\text{ standardized}} = m_{ij}/(m_{pool} + \sum_1^C m_{ij})$, where C is the number of communities. The
187 pool of neighboring species available to colonize a local community was then estimated
188 as the matrixial product of the metacommunity abundance matrix and the standardized
189 migration matrix. The matrix implementation of the coalescent algorithm allowed us to
190 efficiently simulate the assembly of large metacommunities. For all simulations, the
191 species pool was defined at 200 species, and their performance was habitat- and species-
192 dependent (see Figure 1). This number of species in the pool was an arbitrary value
193 defined according to existing empirical studies covering different types of freshwater
194 habitats in the United Kingdom (Biggs et al., 2017) and was used to optimize
195 computational times. However, it should be highlighted that while the absolute magnitude

196 changed, the predicted increase or decrease in diversity and the spatial structure of these
197 changes were not dependent on the size of the species pool considered.

198

199 *Scenarios of landscape dispersal*

200 For each of the three freshwater environments—ephemeral, temporal and permanent—
201 we considered two scenarios modifying the dispersal landscape. First, we estimated the
202 expected geographic diversity pattern for each habitat (ephemeral, temporal and
203 permanent) assuming no dispersal with other habitats (e.g., no dispersal between
204 communities of ephemeral environments and communities of temporal or permanent
205 environments). Second, the same diversity pattern was estimated for each habitat but
206 considered the dispersal among the other two habitats. However, while individuals could
207 colonize different habitats, they were subject to differences in species performances
208 among habitats (Figure 1). Species performance determined the probability of species
209 recruitment into a community belonging to a given freshwater environment. A species-
210 by-community performance matrix P was constructed following the performances
211 presented in Figure 1, with elements p_{ij} representing the recruitment probability of
212 species i in community j . Each element m_{ij} of the migration matrix was multiplied by the
213 element p_{ij} of the performance matrix, determining the action of a species filter for the
214 recruitment in each environment.

215 The difference in richness among local communities when considering the two
216 dispersal scenarios was estimated as the log-ratio (S_{LR}) between the richness observed
217 when dispersal occurred through all freshwater types (S_{all}) and when dispersal occurred
218 only through a unique habitat (S_{unique}): $S_{LR} = \log_{10}(S_{all}/S_{unique})$. Spatially explicit
219 maps of predicted richness in each scenario (S_{unique} and S_{all}) and the associated log-ratio
220 (S_{LR}) were constructed for each kind of freshwater. Finally, a scatter plot of the expected

221 richness with (S_{all}) or without interfreshwater dispersal (S_{equal}) was elaborated.
222 Therefore, the 1:1 relationship indicated a “no effect” of interfreshwater dispersal, and
223 deviations from this relationship indicated that an over- or underrepresentation of species
224 richness occurred when considering only one type of freshwater ecosystem.

225

226 **RESULTS**

227 The coalescent model predicted a large effect of landscape configuration on the spatial
228 trends in diversity for the three types of freshwater environments considered herein
229 (Figure 2). These results indicated that the spatial variation in community size and
230 isolation may promote areas of high and low local diversity. The dispersal among
231 different types of freshwaters indicated a process that enhanced local diversity throughout
232 all considered habitats and thus increased the entire waterscape richness. In particular,
233 permanent freshwater and larger water surfaces (i.e., communities) of all kinds were more
234 positively impacted by dispersal through different types of freshwater habitats.

235 Ephemeral waters presented a wide distribution along the two islands, with higher
236 richness patches along the center and south-east part of the United Kingdom and along
237 the center and west of Ireland (Figure 2A). However, when considering dispersal through
238 other habitats, these hotspots of diversity decreased their spatial extension, but their
239 richness values increased by approximately 150%. Stronger differential values, reporting
240 the change in richness between the three water habitats or only one (i.e., $S_{LR-Ephemeral}$),
241 were detected specifically in the north, along the coast and in the southeast of the United
242 Kingdom. At the geographical level, when comparing the two richness scenarios (S_{all}
243 against S_{unique}) with latitude and longitude (Supplementary Figure 1), we observed an
244 overall change in the pattern described by S_{unique} , with richness slightly increasing in

245 northern regions (slopes of 0.07 for S_{all} against 0.01 for S_{unique}) and western regions
246 (slopes of -0.14 for S_{all} against -0.12 for S_{unique} ; Supplementary Table 1).

247 Temporal waters were widely distributed along the studied islands but with a
248 predominantly northern distribution of higher richness patches (Figure 2B). For these
249 habitats, the magnitude of the effect resulting from considering the whole waterscape was
250 greater than that considering only temporal habitats. These hotspots were located mostly
251 around the north, and their richness values increased by more than 150%. Moreover, the
252 northern increase in richness was clearly highlighted by the $S_{LR-Temporal}$. Additionally,
253 there was a concomitant rise in western and central region richness (slopes of -1.03 for
254 S_{all} and -0.67 for S_{unique} ; Supplementary Figure 1), although this rise remained small in
255 comparison to the latitudinal change (slopes of 1.34 for S_{all} against 0.64 for S_{unique} ;
256 Supplementary Table 1).

257 Permanent waters were more scattered throughout the landscape and therefore
258 were more isolated when considering only their landscape structure (Figure 2C). The
259 consideration of the whole waterscape enhanced species richness in permanent habitats,
260 with an increase in species number close to 200%. Consequently, the differential values
261 considering the three water habitats together ($S_{LR-Permanent}$) were generally high except
262 in the center of the United Kingdom, where a higher density of permanent habitats was
263 already present. The greater geographical change in richness between the two scenarios
264 was mostly concentrated in the western regions (slopes of -1.56 for S_{all} against -0.88 for
265 S_{unique} ; Supplementary Figure 1), while the latitudinal pattern remained similar between
266 the two scenarios (slopes of 0.57 for S_{all} against 0.48 for S_{unique} ; Supplementary Table
267 1).

268 The linear relationships between the predicted richness of one habitat considering
269 only its waterscape (S_{unique}) and the predicted richness when dispersal among freshwater

270 ecosystems is permitted (S_{all}) highlighted the increase in richness because of the effect
271 of individual movement and recruitment among different freshwater habitats (Figure 3).
272 The relationship between these two scenarios was always above the 1:1 relationship for
273 the three ecosystems, indicating that the effect of dispersal always increased species
274 richness. Notably, the slope of these relationships increased with habitat permanence,
275 with ephemeral habitats having a slope of 1.28, temporal habitats having a slope of 1.43
276 and permanent habitats having a slope of 1.91 (Figure 3; Supplementary Table 2).

277

278 **DISCUSSION**

279 The present study adds to an existing mass of evidence supporting a main role of
280 landscape configuration on local and regional diversity (Borthagaray et al., 2012, 2015a,
281 2020; Carrara et al., 2014; Leibold & Chase, 2018; Santos et al., 2019; Rodríguez-Tricot
282 & Arim, 2020). However, our results highlight the seldom recognized importance of
283 dispersal among different environments on metacommunity dynamics (Borthagaray et
284 al., 2018; Williams et al., 2020). From empirical studies at comparatively smaller spatial
285 scales, it is well recognized that the coupling of different freshwater environments by
286 dispersal is a phenomenon that enhances the diversity and resilience of communities
287 (Williams et al., 2004; Gledhill et al., 2008; Biggs et al., 2017; Kelly-Quinn et al., 2017;
288 Hill et al., 2021). Using real landscape information, we have shown how these processes
289 observed at local studies may scale to determine biogeographic diversity patterns (Urban
290 et al., 2016; Carroll et al., 2018; Barnett & Belote, 2021). The increase in local diversity
291 is an expected consequence of the mixing of different species pools (Arim & Barbosa,
292 2002). However, when different species pools arrive in the same community, the mass
293 effect can reduce local diversity because the dominance in regional diversity translates to
294 local dominances fostering species exclusion (Mouquet & Loreau 2002, Leibold et al.,

295 2004, Loreau 2010, Borthagaray et al., 2015; Leibold & Chase, 2018). While this negative
296 effect was observed in a few areas, the main expectation is a positive effect on local
297 diversity because of the flow of individuals between freshwater types. However, habitat
298 homogenization involving the selection of the same species in different communities, or
299 the dominance of invasive species are processes that may foster regional and local
300 dominance. This scenario can determine a negative effect from inter-freshwater
301 connections. Our analyses also indicated the existence of a strong spatial structure in the
302 potential effect of dispersal among different freshwater environments. This result
303 indicates that freshwater biogeography is probably determined by the connection among
304 freshwater ecosystems to a larger extent than previously thought. This is particularly
305 important if it is noted that most empirical and theoretical studies consider the role of
306 different freshwater landscapes in isolation—e.g., pondscapes, riverscapes, lakes, and
307 wetlands.

308 Our modeling approach specifically focused on the essential features of the
309 coupling of freshwater environments by dispersal. However, this is a much more complex
310 phenomenon with several areas that may demand further attention in future studies. On
311 the one hand, dispersal depends on species traits such as body size (De Bie et al., 2012),
312 and species from different environments may have larger differences in dispersal
313 capacities (e.g., odonates from ephemeral waters and fish from permanent waters).
314 Coupling among communities may consequently be asymmetric, resulting in some
315 environments operating as sources and others operating as sink communities (Hanski,
316 1999). Similarly, as dispersal does not equally affect all species, some organisms could
317 be strongly and directly affected by landscape configuration, while others are weakly or
318 only indirectly affected (Urban & Keitt, 2001; Grainger & Gilbert, 2016; Cunillera-
319 Montcusí et al., 2021). The effect of the coupling of different ecosystems is probably

320 contingent on these determinants of dispersal. In addition, temporal insurance is a further
321 mechanism to be considered. The temporal decoupling in the occurrence of different
322 freshwater environments may be important for species persistence on the landscape. For
323 example, organisms survive in more persistent freshwaters in the dry phases of temporal
324 ecosystems. However, diversity emerges from a balance and interaction between
325 dispersal and other forces, such as selection, drift, and speciation-extinction history
326 (Vellend, 2016). The present study provides a framework for better understanding the
327 dispersal component on this balance but also highlights the need to better understand all
328 of them by means of empirical and/or theoretical approaches.

329 Species may be more adapted to a particular environment, but they can use
330 suboptimal environments, enhancing their representation in the landscape and by this
331 means, their abundance in local communities (Williams et al., 2020). Even when the
332 occurrence of these species in suboptimal waters could be limited in time and become
333 excluded after some generations, they may use these less suitable habitats as stepping-
334 stone paths in the flow of individuals between suitable environments (Keitt, 1997; Urban
335 & Keitt, 2001; Uroy et al., 2021). In addition, the incoming dispersal reduces the
336 extinction rate in local communities or ensures recolonization if extinctions occur
337 (Hanski, 1999; Leibold & Chase, 2018). Here, it was shown that the combination of the
338 mass effect and stepping-stone dispersal fostered diversity in the three types of
339 ephemeral, temporal, and permanent habitats. However, this increase was greater for
340 permanent habitats than for the other two types. The distribution of permanent waters was
341 more scattered, and the landscape was more fragmented. This created a higher isolation
342 for these habitats that led to smaller diversity values when permanent habitats were
343 considered. However, the whole waterscape provided a landscape in which species
344 flowed among permanent communities through temporal or ephemeral ones. In addition,

345 permanent water may experience an increase in local diversity by the persistence of
346 species from temporal and ephemeral waters surviving in permanent waters by a mass
347 effect. Overall, these results highlighted the important role of seasonal habitats (e.g.,
348 temporary ponds, temporary rivers, shallow seasonal wetlands), which are more abundant
349 throughout the landscape (Downing et al., 2006), as stepping stones for species to reach
350 more permanent, stable, and larger habitats (Crghino et al., 2008; Hill et al., 2021).

351 Part of the biota of a specific habitat, such as a pond or river, interacts more or
352 less strongly with other freshwater habitats, making these other habitats key determinants
353 of the landscape that such species perceive and use (Williams et al., 2004; Borthagaray
354 et al., 2015b). Nevertheless, the relevance of the waterscape is still not clear or has been
355 poorly assessed (Hill et al., 2021). We observed that not considering the entire waterscape
356 could underestimate the biodiversity in all habitats, especially for larger, permanent, and
357 isolated habitats, as well as for more widely distributed habitats along the landscape, such
358 as temporal or ephemeral waters. In a global change scenario of a generalized loss of
359 water throughout all types of freshwater habitats, more humid regions might not lose the
360 same total amount of water surfaces, but these surfaces might become more seasonal or
361 disappear due to human intervention (Wood et al., 2003; IPCC, 2014). Such a process
362 implies that as global change continues, permanent habitats will become increasingly
363 isolated, and the waterscape will become increasingly fragmented (Arntzen et al., 2017;
364 Horvth et al., 2019). Consequently, integrating the waterscape by categorizing its waters
365 according to seasonality represents a key approach if a wide regional assessment of
366 freshwater biodiversity should be pursued, especially to preserve overall system
367 resilience (Chase et al., 2020; Cid et al., 2020). In this sense, based on our results, western
368 communities in the northern region (i.e., the island of Ireland) might be highly dependent
369 on dispersal across different habitats, and more generally, the diversity of permanent

370 habitats might be greatly dependent on ephemeral and temporal habitat landscape cover.
371 Such relevance emphasizes the importance of acknowledging not only one aquatic habitat
372 (e.g., permanent) when any conservation policy is to be planned.

373 The integration of the landscape perspective must also consider species
374 differences in performance between habitat types. Seasonality is one key determinant of
375 all types of freshwater habitats, both flowing (Datry et al., 2014; Rosset et al., 2017) and
376 still (Díaz-Paniagua et al., 2010; Fernández-Zamudio et al., 2016; O'Neill, 2016; Shin &
377 Kneitel, 2019). Therefore, it determines which organisms can inhabit each habitat and the
378 interaction that they will have with other types (Wiggins et al., 1980; Tachet, 2000),
379 whether the interaction is sporadic (e.g., stepping-stones for dispersal) or recurrent
380 (nesting or foraging grounds). Thus, it is interesting to include community differentiation
381 and/or habitat-specific performances within future models (Munoz et al., 2018; Cunillera-
382 Montcusí et al., 2021). Including such differences between species in performance
383 according to the type of habitat toward which they disperse or the temporal availability
384 of these habitats according to their seasonality (e.g., temporally explicit coalescent
385 models) will help to better depict the regional biodiversity patterns, acknowledging the
386 waterscape and as well as the intrinsic differences across habitats.

387 This study attempts to provide a general guide about the biogeographic
388 consequences of dispersal among freshwater environments in general and in the United
389 Kingdom and Ireland in particular (Biggs et al., 2017; Hill et al., 2021). However,
390 assumptions about the size of the species pool, species performances and dispersal pattern
391 are involved. Previous sections discussed the robustness of our results and its
392 extrapolation to alternative scenarios. For further inferring the effect of inter-
393 environments dispersal in other scenarios the focus has to be put on its consequence on
394 the mass effect. Essentially, the larger the size, diversity, dispersal from the source species

395 pool, and the lower the ecological differences between source and sink communities, the
396 larger the mass effect will be (Hanski 1999; Loreau 2010; Leibold and Chase 2018;
397 Suzuki and Economo 2021). Consequently, the patterns herein reported can be
398 qualitatively translated to other scenarios considering how these forces beyond the mass
399 effect are affected.

400 In light of our results, it has to be highlighted that legislation often ignores small
401 water bodies, and the United Kingdom and Ireland are not exceptions (Hill et al., 2017b,
402 2021). Here, we show that in addition to hosting substantial biodiversity, pondscapes
403 provide routes for the dispersal of organisms that inhabit other freshwaters, improving
404 their diversity and resilience (Cunillera-Montcusí et al., 2021). Thus, we show that the
405 waterscape plays an important role in shaping diversity patterns across regions and that
406 considering this role would contribute to greater overall diversities in all types of
407 freshwater habitats. The present theoretical analysis, focused on a large geographic scale,
408 complements and supports previous studies performed at comparatively more local scales
409 (Gledhill et al., 2008; Biggs et al., 2017; Hill et al., 2017b; Williams et al., 2020). The
410 consistent message is that dispersal through different kinds of freshwater habitats (i.e.,
411 waterscapes) may foster local diversity in specific freshwater communities (e.g., ponds,
412 lakes, rivers). In addition, we want to emphasize the poorly recognized role of dispersal
413 through different kinds of ecosystems, which should be a matter of concern in
414 metacommunity theory. Furthermore, this inter-freshwater dispersal may have an
415 important role in shaping geographic patterns of biodiversity in the United Kingdom and
416 Ireland as well as in other regions. These results constitute a step forward in incorporating
417 regional-scale approximations into management and biodiversity conservation. In the
418 current global change context, landscape management from a mechanistic understanding

419 of its connection with biodiversity represents a promising path for ensuring ecosystem
420 resilience.

421

422

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438 **REFERENCES**

- 439 Arim, M., & O. Barbosa, 2002. Humped Pattern of Diversity: Fact or Artifact? *Science* 297: 1763,
440 doi: 10.1126/science.297.5588.1763a.
- 441 Altermatt, F., 2013. Diversity in riverine metacommunities: A network perspective. *Aquatic*
442 *Ecology* 47: 365–377.
- 443 Arntzen, J. W., C. Abrahams, W. R. M. Meilink, R. Iosif, & A. Zuiderwijk, 2017. Amphibian
444 decline, pond loss and reduced population connectivity under agricultural intensification over a
445 38 year period. *Biodiversity and Conservation Springer Netherlands* 26: 1411–1430.

- 446 Barnett, K., & R. T. Belote, 2021. Modeling an aspirational connected network of protected areas
447 across North America. *Ecological Applications* 31:,
448 <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/eap.2387>.
- 449 Bastin, L., N. Gorelick, S. Saura, B. Bertzky, G. Dubois, M. J. Fortin, & J. F. Pekel, 2019. Inland
450 surface waters in protected areas globally: Current coverage and 30-year trends. *PLoS ONE* 14:
451 1–17.
- 452 Bender, M. G., F. Leprieur, D. Mouillot, M. Kulbicki, V. Parravicini, M. R. Pie, D. R. Barneche,
453 L. G. R. Oliveira-Santos, & S. R. Floeter, 2017. Isolation drives taxonomic and functional
454 nestedness in tropical reef fish faunas. *Ecography* 40: 425–435.
- 455 Biggs, J., S. von Fumetti, & M. Kelly-Quinn, 2017. The importance of small waterbodies for
456 biodiversity and ecosystem services: implications for policy makers. *Hydrobiologia Springer*
457 *International Publishing* 793: 3–39.
- 458 Boix, D., J. Kneitel, B. J. Robson, C. Duchet, L. Zúñiga, J. Day, S. Gascón, J. Sala, X. D.
459 Quintana, & L. Blaustein, 2016. Invertebrates of Freshwater Temporary Ponds in Mediterranean
460 Climates In Batzer, D. P., & D. Boix (eds), *Invertebrates in Freshwater Wetlands. An international*
461 *Perspective on their Ecology*. Springer International Publishing, Cham: 141–190.
- 462 Borthagaray, A. I., M. Arim, & P. A. Marquet, 2012. Connecting landscape structure and patterns
463 in body size distributions. *Oikos* 121: 697–710.
- 464 Borthagaray, A. I., V. Pinelli, M. Berazategui, L. Rodríguez-Tricot, & M. Arim, 2015a. Effects
465 of metacommunity networks on local community structures: from theoretical predictions to
466 empirical evaluations In Belgrano, A., G. Woodward, & U. Jacob (eds), *Aquatic Functional*
467 *Biodiversity*. Academic Press, Oxford: 75–111.
- 468 Borthagaray, A. I., M. Berazategui, & M. Arim, 2015b. Disentangling the effects of local and
469 regional processes on biodiversity patterns through taxon-contingent metacommunity network
470 analysis. *Oikos* 124: 1383–1390, <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/oik.01317>.
- 471 Borthagaray, A. I., A. Soutullo, A. Carranza, & M. Arim, 2018. A modularity-based approach for
472 identifying biodiversity management units. *Revista Chilena de Historia Natural Revista Chilena*
473 *de Historia Natural* 91: 11–15.
- 474 Borthagaray, A. I., F. Teixeira-de Mello, G. Tesitore, E. Ortiz, M. Illarze, V. Pinelli, L. Urtado,
475 P. Raftopoulos, I. González-Bergonzoni, S. Abades, M. Loureiro, & M. Arim, 2020. Community
476 isolation drives lower fish biomass and species richness, but higher functional evenness, in a river
477 metacommunity. *Freshwater Biology* 1–15.
- 478 Brown, J. H., & A. Kodric-Brown, 1977. Turnover Rates in Insular Biogeography: Effect of
479 Immigration on Extinction. *Ecology* 58: 445–449.
- 480 Buono, V., A. M. Bissattini, & L. Vignoli, 2019. Can a cow save a newt? The role of cattle
481 drinking troughs in amphibian conservation. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater*
482 *Ecosystems* 29: 964–975, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/aqc.3126>.
- 483 Carrara, F., A. Rinaldo, A. Giometto, & F. Altermatt, 2014. Complex interaction of dendritic
484 connectivity and hierarchical patch size on biodiversity in river-like landscapes. *American*
485 *Naturalist* 183: 13–25.
- 486 Carroll, C., S. A. Parks, S. Z. Dobrowski, & D. R. Roberts, 2018. Climatic, topographic, and
487 anthropogenic factors determine connectivity between current and future climate analogs in North
488 America. *Global Change Biology* 24: 5318–5331.
- 489 Céréghino, R., J. Biggs, B. Oertli, & S. Declerck, 2008. The ecology of European ponds: Defining
490 the characteristics of a neglected freshwater habitat. *Hydrobiologia* 597: 1–6.

- 491 Chase, J. M., & R. S. Shulman, 2009. Wetland isolation facilitates larval mosquito density through
492 the reduction of predators. *Ecological Entomology* 34: 741–747.
- 493 Chase, J. M., A. Jeliaskov, E. Ladouceur, & D. S. Viana, 2020. Biodiversity conservation through
494 the lens of metacommunity ecology. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 1469: 86–
495 104.
- 496 Cid, N., N. Bonada, J. Heino, M. Cañedo-Argüelles, J. Crabot, R. Sarremejane, J. Soininen, R.
497 Stubbington, & T. Datry, 2020. A metacommunity approach to improve biological assessments
498 in highly dynamic freshwater ecosystems. *BioScience* 70: 427–438.
- 499 Cunillera-Montcusí, D., A. I. Borthagaray, D. Boix, S. Gascón, J. Sala, I. Tornero, X. D. Quintana,
500 & M. Arim, 2021. Metacommunity resilience against simulated gradients of wildfire: disturbance
501 intensity and species dispersal ability determine landscape recover capacity. *Ecography* 44: 1022–
502 1034.
- 503 Datry, T., S. T. Larned, & K. Tockner, 2014. Intermittent rivers: A challenge for freshwater
504 ecology. *BioScience* 64: 229–235.
- 505 Davis, C. A., & J. R. Bidwell, 2008. Response of aquatic invertebrates to vegetation management
506 and agriculture. *Wetlands* 28: 793–805.
- 507 De Bie, T., L. De Meester, L. Brendonck, K. Martens, B. Goddeeris, D. Ercken, H. Hampel, L.
508 Denys, L. Vanhecke, K. Van der Gucht, J. Van Wichelen, W. Vyverman, & S. A. J. Declerck,
509 2012. Body size and dispersal mode as key traits determining metacommunity structure of aquatic
510 organisms. *Ecology Letters* 15: 740–747.
- 511 Deil, U., 2005. A review on habitats, plant traits and vegetation of ephemeral wetlands-a global
512 perspective. *Phytocoenologia* 35: 533–705.
- 513 Díaz-Paniagua, C., R. Fernández-Zamudio, M. Florencio, P. García-Murillo, C. Gómez-
514 Rodríguez, A. Porthault, L. Serrano, & P. Siljeström, 2010. Temporary ponds from Doñana
515 National Park: A system of natural habitats for the preservation of aquatic flora and fauna.
516 *Limnetica* 29: 41–58.
- 517 Downing, J. A., Y. T. Prairie, J. J. Cole, C. M. Duarte, L. J. Tranvik, R. G. Striegl, W. H.
518 McDowell, P. Kortelainen, N. F. Caraco, J. M. Melack, & J. J. Middelburg, 2006. The global
519 abundance and size distribution of lakes, ponds, and impoundments. *Limnology and*
520 *Oceanography* 51: 2388–2397.
- 521 Economo, E. P., & T. H. Keitt, 2008. Species diversity in neutral metacommunities: A network
522 approach. *Ecology Letters* 11: 52–62.
- 523 Economo, E. P., & T. H. Keitt, 2010. Network isolation and local diversity in neutral
524 metacommunities. *Oikos* 119: 1355–1363.
- 525 ESRI Inc., 2020. ArcGIS Pro. , <https://www.esri.com/en-us/arcgis/products/arcgis-pro/overview>.
- 526 Fernández-Zamudio, R., P. García-Murillo, & C. Díaz-Paniagua, 2016. Aquatic plant distribution
527 is driven by physical and chemical variables and hydroperiod in a mediterranean temporary pond
528 network. *Hydrobiologia* 774: 123–135.
- 529 Gledhill, D. G., P. James, & D. H. Davies, 2008. Pond density as a determinant of aquatic species
530 richness in an urban landscape. *Landscape Ecology* 23: 1219–1230.
- 531 Grainger, T. N., & B. Gilbert, 2016. Dispersal and diversity in experimental metacommunities:
532 linking theory and practice. *Oikos* 125: 1213–1223.
- 533 Haddad, N. M., L. A. Brudvig, J. Clobert, K. F. Davies, A. Gonzalez, R. D. Holt, T. E. Lovejoy,
534 J. O. Sexton, M. P. Austin, C. D. Collins, W. M. Cook, E. I. Damschen, R. M. Ewers, B. L. Foster,

- 535 C. N. Jenkins, A. J. King, W. F. Laurance, D. J. Levey, C. R. Margules, B. A. Melbourne, A. O.
536 Nicholls, J. L. Orrock, D. X. Song, & J. R. Townshend, 2015. Habitat fragmentation and its lasting
537 impact on Earth's ecosystems. *Science Advances* 1: 1–10.
- 538 Halley, J. M., & Y. Iwasa, 2011. Neutral theory as a predictor of avifaunal extinctions after habitat
539 loss. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 108: 2316–2321.
- 540 Hanski, I., 1999. Habitat Connectivity, Habitat Continuity, and Metapopulations in Dynamic
541 Landscapes. *Oikos* 87: 209.
- 542 Heino, J., J. Alahuhta, L. M. Bini, Y. Cai, A. S. Heiskanen, S. Hellsten, P. Kortelainen, N.
543 Kotamäki, K. T. Tolonen, P. Vihervaara, A. Vilmi, & D. G. Angeler, 2021. Lakes in the era of
544 global change: moving beyond single-lake thinking in maintaining biodiversity and ecosystem
545 services. *Biological Reviews* 96: 89–106.
- 546 Hill, M. J., J. Heino, I. Thornhill, D. B. Ryves, & P. J. Wood, 2017a. Effects of dispersal mode
547 on the environmental and spatial correlates of nestedness and species turnover in pond
548 communities. *Oikos* 126: 1575–1585.
- 549 Hill, M. J., R. G. Death, K. L. Mathers, D. B. Ryves, J. C. White, & P. J. Wood, 2017b.
550 Macroinvertebrate community composition and diversity in ephemeral and perennial ponds on
551 unregulated floodplain meadows in the UK. *Hydrobiologia Springer International Publishing* 793:
552 95–108.
- 553 Hill, M. J., H. M. Greaves, C. D. Sayer, C. Hassall, M. Milin, V. S. Milner, L. Marazzi, R. Hall,
554 L. R. Harper, I. Thornhill, R. Walton, J. Biggs, N. Ewald, A. Law, N. Willby, J. C. White, R. A.
555 Briers, K. L. Mathers, M. J. Jeffries, & P. J. Wood, 2021. Pond ecology and conservation: research
556 priorities and knowledge gaps. *Ecosystems* .
- 557 Horváth, Z., R. Ptacnik, C. F. Vad, & J. M. Chase, 2019. Habitat loss over six decades accelerates
558 regional and local biodiversity loss via changing landscape connectance. *Ecology Letters* 22:
559 1019–1027.
- 560 IPCC, 2014. *Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part A: Global and*
561 *Sectoral Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the*
562 *Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth*
563 *Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge University*
564 *Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA,*
565 *papers2://publication/uuid/B8BF5043-C873-4AFD-97F9-A630782E590D.*
- 566 Keitt, T. H., 1997. Stability and complexity on a lattice: Coexistence of species in an individual-
567 based food web model. *Ecological Modelling* 102: 243–258.
- 568 Kelly-Quinn, M., J. Biggs, & S. von Fumetti, 2017. Preface: The importance of small water
569 bodies. *Hydrobiologia Springer International Publishing* 793: 1–2.
- 570 Leibold, M.A., Holyoak, M., Mouquet, N., Amarasekare, P., Chase, J.M., Hoopes, M.F., Holt, R.
571 D., Shurin, J. B., Law, T., Tilman, D., & M., Loreau, 2004. The metacommunity concept: a
572 framework for multi-scale community ecology. *Ecology Letters* 7: 601–613.
- 573 Leibold, M. A., & J. M. Chase, 2018. *Metacommunity Ecology*. Princeton University Press.
- 574 Loreau, M., 2010. *From population to ecosystems: theoretical foundations for a new ecological*
575 *synthesis*. Princeton University Press, Oxford and Princeton.
- 576 Matias, M. G., N. Mouquet, & J. M. Chase, 2013. Dispersal stochasticity mediates species
577 richness in source-sink metacommunities. *Oikos* 122: 395–402.
- 578 Miró, A., D. O'Brien, J. Tomàs, T. Buchaca, I. Sabás, V. Osorio, F. Lucati, Q. Pou-Rovira, & M.
579 Ventura, 2020. Rapid amphibian community recovery following removal of non-native fish from

580 high mountain lakes. *Biological Conservation* Elsevier 251: 108783,
581 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108783>.

582 Mouquet, N., & M. Loreau, 2002. Coexistence in metacommunities: the regional similarity
583 hypothesis. *The American Naturalist* 159: 420-426.

584 Munoz, F., M. Grenié, P. Denelle, A. Taudière, F. Laroche, C. Tucker, & C. Violle, 2018.
585 ecolottery: Simulating and assessing community assembly with environmental filtering and
586 neutral dynamics in R. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 9: 693–703.

587 O’Neill, B. J., 2016. Community disassembly in ephemeral ecosystems. *Ecology* 97: 3285–3292.

588 Pekel, J. F., A. Cottam, N. Gorelick, & A. S. Belward, 2016. High-resolution mapping of global
589 surface water and its long-term changes. *Nature* Nature Publishing Group 540: 418–422,
590 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/nature20584>.

591 Rodríguez-Tricot, L., & M. Arim, 2020. From Hutchinsonian ratios to spatial scaling theory: the
592 interplay among limiting similarity, body size and landscape structure. *Ecography* 43: 318–327.

593 Rosset, V., A. Ruhi, M. T. Bogan, & T. Datry, 2017. Do lentic and lotic communities respond
594 similarly to drying?. *Ecosphere* 8: e01809.

595 Santos, M., L. Cagnolo, T. Roslin, H. J. Marrero, & D. P. Vázquez, 2019. Landscape connectivity
596 explains interaction network patterns at multiple scales. *Ecology* 100: 1–8.

597 Seymour, M., E. A. Fronhofer, & F. Altermatt, 2015. Dendritic network structure and dispersal
598 affect temporal dynamics of diversity and species persistence. *Oikos* 124: 908–916.

599 Shin, H. R., & J. M. Kneitel, 2019. Warming interacts with inundation timing to influence the
600 species composition of California vernal pool communities. *Hydrobiologia* Springer International
601 Publishing 0123456789:, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-019-04040-z>.

602 Shipley, B., F. De Bello, J. H. C. Cornelissen, E. Laliberté, D. C. Laughlin, & P. B. Reich, 2016.
603 Reinforcing loose foundation stones in trait-based plant ecology. *Oecologia* Springer Berlin
604 Heidelberg 180: 923–931.

605 Suzuki, Y., & Economo, E. P. (2021). From species sorting to mass effects: spatial network
606 structure mediates the shift between metacommunity archetypes. *Ecography*, 44: 715-726.

607 Tachet, H., 2000. *Invertebrés d’eau douce, systématique, biologie, écologie*. CNR Editions, Paris,
608 Paris.

609 Thompson, P. L., B. Rayfield, & A. Gonzalez, 2017. Loss of habitat and connectivity erodes
610 species diversity, ecosystem functioning, and stability in metacommunity networks. *Ecography*
611 40: 98–108.

612 Tittensor, D.P., & B. Worm, 2016. A neutral-metabolic theory of latitudinal biodiversity. *Global*
613 *Ecol. Biogeogr.* 25: 630-641.

614 Urban, D. L., & T. H. Keitt, 2001. Landscape connectivity: A graph-theoretic perspective.
615 *Ecology* 85: 1205–1218.

616 Urban, M. C., G. Bocedi, A. P. Hendry, J.-B. Mihoub, G. Pe’er, A. Singer, J. R. Bridle, L. G.
617 Crozier, L. De Meester, W. Godsoe, A. Gonzalez, J. J. Hellmann, R. D. Holt, A. Huth, K. Johst,
618 C. B. Krug, P. W. Leadley, S. C. F. Palmer, J. H. Pantel, A. Schmitz, P. A. Zollner, & J. M. J.
619 Travis, 2016. Improving the forecast for biodiversity under climate change. *Science* 353:
620 aad8466.

621 Uroy, L., A. Alignier, C. Mony, J. C. Foltête, & A. Ernoult, 2021. How to assess the temporal
622 dynamics of landscape connectivity in ever-changing landscapes: a literature review. *Landscape*
623 *Ecology* 36: 2487–2504.

- 624 Vellend, 2016. *The Theory of Ecological Communities*. Princeton University Press.
- 625 Wiggins, G. B. B., R. J. J. Mackay, & I. M. M. Smith, 1980. Evolutionary and ecological
626 strategies of animals in annual temporary pools. *Archiv für Hydrobiologie supplement* 58: 97–
627 206.
- 628 Williams, D. D., 2006. *The Biology of temporary waters*. Oxford University Press,
629 http://cataleg.udg.edu/record=b1216539~S10*cat.
- 630 Williams, P., J. Biggs, C. Stoate, J. Szczur, C. Brown, & S. Bonney, 2020. Nature based measures
631 increase freshwater biodiversity in agricultural catchments. *Biological Conservation Elsevier*
632 244: 108515, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108515>.
- 633 Williams, P., M. Whitfield, J. Biggs, S. Bray, G. Fox, P. Nicolet, & D. Sear, 2004. Comparative
634 biodiversity of rivers, streams, ditches and ponds in an agricultural landscape in Southern
635 England. *Biological Conservation* 115: 329–341,
636 <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0006320703001538>.
- 637 Wood, P. J., M. T. Greenwood, & M. D. Agnew, 2003. Pond biodiversity and habitat loss in the
638 UK. *Area* 35: 206–216, <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/1475-4762.00249>.
- 639 Worm, B., & D. P. Tittensor, 2018. *A Theory of Global Biodiversity*. Princeton University Press.
- 640

641 **Figure captions**

642 **Figure 1:** Simulated species performances along ephemeral, temporal, and permanent
643 freshwaters. The x-axis is the species ID—an identification number—and the y-axis is
644 the species performance. Performance bias indicated the recruitment of individuals of
645 each species in each freshwater environment in the coalescent assembly of communities.

646

647

648 **Figure 1.** Simulated species performances along ephemeral, temporal, and permanent
 649 freshwaters. The x-axis is the species ID—an identification number—and the y-axis is the species
 650 performance. Performance bias indicated the recruitment of individuals of each species in each
 651 freshwater environment in the coalescent assembly of communities.

A) Ephemeral freshwater ecosystem

i. Dispersal only through ephemeral habitats

ii. Dispersal through ephemeral, temporal and permanent habitats

iii. Richness log-ratio: $\log_{10}(S_{all}/S_{unique})$

B) Temporal freshwater ecosystem

i. Dispersal only through temporal habitats

ii. Dispersal through ephemeral, temporal and permanent habitats

iii. Richness log-ratio: $\log_{10}(S_{all}/S_{unique})$

C) Permanent freshwater ecosystem

i. Dispersal only through permanent habitats

ii. Dispersal through ephemeral, temporal and permanent habitats

iii. Richness log-ratio: $\log_{10}(S_{all}/S_{unique})$

652

653 **Figure 2.** Expected richness in ephemeral (A), temporal (B) and permanent freshwaters
654 (C) for the United Kingdom and Ireland in a grid cell (10×10 km). Richness was estimated
655 with a coalescent model that considered dispersal only (i) through the same freshwater
656 environment— S_{unique} —or (ii) through the different kinds of freshwater environments
657 (ephemeral, temporal and permanent)— S_{all} . The log ratio between these two estimations
658 (iii)— S_{LR} —indicates the relative effect of dispersal between freshwater environments on
659 diversity.

660

661

662 **Figure 3.** Effect of the connection among freshwater environments on local diversity as
663 a function of local diversity when this connection does not occur. The red dashed line
664 indicates the 1:1 relationship—e.g., no effect of interfreshwater dispersal. Scatterplots
665 show that the coupling between different types of environments foster local diversity in
666 a magnitude that increases from ephemeral to permanent waters and from poorer to richer
667 communities.